

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates:
1 – 14 July 2023

Report published: January 2025

Love / hate relationships: Monitoring
the return of the wolf to the German
state of Lower Saxony

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ABSTRACT

This report details wolf *Canis lupus lupus* active monitoring fieldwork by Biosphere Expeditions in collaboration with the State Wolf Bureau of the German state of Lower Saxony, local foresters and wolf commissioners. Field work was conducted from 1 to 14 July 2023 in two one-week long groups, each comprising twelve citizen scientists. The aim of the expedition was to collect samples for DNA and dietary analyses. This was done by sending small groups into the field to search for scat samples. The study area covered various priority areas in Lower Saxony as advised or requested by the State Wolf Bureau, wolf commissioners, hunters and the State Forestry Authority. Twenty-two individual 10 km x 10 km grid cells of the [European Environment Agency \(EEA\) reference grid system](#) were surveyed on foot, some of them multiple times, covering almost 800 km.

The expedition collected 259 wolf scat samples, 216 of which were included into the official wolf monitoring programme. Of these, 155 samples were frozen for dietary analysis and 16 were fresh enough for DNA analysis. Fifteen (7%) of the 216 scat samples were classified as C1 pieces of hard evidence on the SCALP classification system, 28 (13%) as C2 confirmed observation and 164 (76%) as C3 unconfirmed observations. Other signs of wolf presence, such as three tracks (C3), were also found during the expedition. One sighting was also recorded and assessed as a C3 piece of unconfirmed evidence. Dietary analysis is ongoing.

The DNA analysis of the 16 samples showed that 15 scats originated from wolf (no species could be determined for one scat, because it was too old). Six samples could be assigned to individual wolves; for nine samples the species wolf, but no particular individual, could be identified. In all, nine male wolves and two female wolves were identified, In three more cases, the sex was unclear, but probably male. Two male individuals were logged for the first time through the expedition.

The quantity and quality of samples collected by these annual citizen scientist expeditions continues to be remarkable. This year the expedition, over the course of two weeks of intensive citizen scientist effort, contributed 14% of all samples collected all year by the state of Lower Saxony's official wolf monitoring programme. The average contribution of the expedition over the years 2017 - 2023 is 21%, or a fifth of all samples. Over the same period, the amount of C1 (hard evidence) scats collected by the expedition was 42% of all C1 scats collected all year by the state of Lower Saxony's official wolf monitoring programme. This clearly demonstrates the power of citizen science and the very significant contribution it makes to wolf research and conservation in Lower Saxony.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Der vorliegende Expeditionsbericht fasst die Ergebnisse der Geländearbeit von Biosphere Expeditions im Rahmen eines aktiven Monitorings der Tierart Wolf (*Canis lupus*) in Zusammenarbeit mit dem Wolfsbüro des Landes Niedersachsen sowie lokalen Förstern und Wolfsberatern zusammen. Die Expedition fand im Zeitraum 01. – 14. Juli 2023 in zwei Gruppen mit jeweils zwölf Personen statt, die die Geländearbeiten für jeweils eine Woche durchführten. Ziel der Expedition war es, Losungsproben für genetische Untersuchungen und Nahrungsanalysen zu sammeln. Dazu wurden kleine Gruppen in Regionen mit bestätigten bzw. mit vermuteten Wolfsvorkommen geschickt. Das Untersuchungsgebiet umfasste verschiedene Gebiete in Niedersachsen, die in Rücksprache mit dem Wolfsbüro der Oberen Naturschutzbehörde, Wolfsberatern, Jägern und dem Niedersächsischen Landesforst vereinbart wurden. 22 Rasterzellen des [European Environment Agency \(EEA\) Rasters](#) wurden im Rahmen der Expedition zu Fuß, einige davon mehrfach, abgedeckt, wobei nahezu 800 km zurückgelegt wurden.

Insgesamt wurden 259 Losungsproben gesammelt, von denen 216 in das offizielle Wolfsmonitoring des Landes einfließen. 155 der 216 Proben wurden für Nahrungsanalysen eingefroren, 16 Proben waren frisch genug, um sie für genetische Untersuchungen zu beproben. 15 (7%) der 216 Kotproben wurden als eindeutige Wolfsnachweise (C1) bewertet, 28 (13%) als bestätigte Wolfshinweise (C2) und 164 (76%) als unbestätigte Hinweise (C3). Außerdem wurden drei Spuren (C3) und eine Beobachtung (C3) als weitere Hinweise auf Wolfspräsenz im Rahmen der Expedition dokumentiert. Die Nahrungsanalysen dauern noch an.

15 der 16 Genetikproben konnten im Rahmen der genetischen Untersuchungen der Tierart Wolf zugeordnet werden (bei einer Probe konnte aufgrund des Alters keine Tierart mehr bestimmt werden). Insgesamt wurden neun männliche sowie zwei weibliche Wölfe identifiziert, in weiteren drei Fällen konnte das Geschlecht nicht ganz eindeutig bestimmt werden, vermutlich handelte es sich hierbei aber um männliche Individuen. Sechs dieser 15 Proben konnten Wolfsindividuen zugeordnet werden, bei einer Probe war die Individualisierung nicht eindeutig. Zwei Wolfsruden wurden im Rahmen der Expedition erstmalig in Niedersachsen nachgewiesen.

Die Menge und Qualität der im Rahmen der jährlich stattfindenden Geländeuntersuchungen von Bürgerwissenschaftlern zum Wolf in Niedersachsen ist nach wie vor beachtlich. In diesem Jahr trug die Expedition im Laufe von zwei Wochen intensiver Arbeit der Bürgerwissenschaftler 14 % aller Proben bei, die das ganze Jahr über durch das offizielle Wolfsmonitoringprogramm des Landes Niedersachsen gesammelt wurden. Der durchschnittliche Anteil über die vergangenen Expeditionsjahre 2017 - 2023 liegt bei 21% bzw. bei einem Fünftel aller Proben. Im gleichen Zeitraum beträgt der Anteil der Kotproben, die mit C1 (eindeutiger Nachweis) bewertet wurden, 42% aller im Rahmen des offiziellen Wolfsmonitorings gesammelten C1 Losungsfunde. Dies zeigt deutlich die Bedeutung der Bürgerwissenschaft und ihren enormen Beitrag zur Wolfsforschung und zum Wolfsschutz in Niedersachsen.

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1. Expedition review

M. Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background & research area

Background information, location conditions and the research area are as per Schütte & Hammer (2018), Schütte & Hammer (2019), Schütte, Steinberg & Hammer (2020) and Schütte, Steinberg & Hammer (2023). The aim of the expedition was to actively monitor for wolf *Canis lupus lupus* signs such as scats and tracks so that wolf ecology and population dynamics (wolf and pack numbers, group sizes, movements, diet) can be elucidated to mitigate human-wolf conflict.

For the 2023 expedition, the expedition base changed to [NaturCampus Bockum](#).

1.2. Dates & team

The 2023 expedition ran over a period of two weeks divided into two 7-day groups, each composed of a team of national and international citizen scientists, a local wolf commissioner and other helpers, two scientists and an expedition leader. Group dates were as shown in the team list below.

The expedition team was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

1-7 July 2023: Maria Aragon (Spain), Jim Blomgren (USA), Lulu Brandt (USA), Carine Coetzee (Australia), Sieglinde Dittmann (Germany), Sylvia Dittmann (Germany), Silke Kutzer (Germany), Anne Schroedter (Germany), Nic Simpson (UK), Patricia Smith (Belgium), Lousia Ulrich-Verderber (USA).

8-14 July 2023: Lulu Brandt (USA), Sylvia Dittmann (Germany), Sieglinde Dittmann (Germany), David Lane (UK), Jess Lane (UK), Jana Lippmann (Germany), Marianne McCoshen (USA), Vincent Schaller (Sweden), Rebecca Schmidt (Germany), Patricia Smith (Belgium), Emily Storey (UK), Sabine Unbescheid (Germany).

In addition for some or all of the time: Peter Schütte and Charlotte Steinberg (expedition scientists), An Bollen (expedition leader) and wolf commissioner Kenny Kenner.

A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place, but did not have to be invoked as there were no medical incidents.

1.3. Partners

Biosphere Expeditions' main partner on this expedition was the state's environmental authority the [NLWKN](#) (Niedersächsischer Landesbetrieb für Wasserwirtschaft, Küsten- und Naturschutz, Nature = Lower Saxony Water Management, Coastal Defence and Nature Conservation Agency), which is officially responsible for the monitoring of all wildlife in the state. The authority's [Wolfsbüro](#) (wolf bureau) staff were closely involved in all expedition activities. Other partners included the [Landesforsten](#) (state forestry department), district and communal authorities, [BIO-Hotel Kenners LandLust](#), [Wolfcenter Dörverden](#) and [NaturCampus Bockum](#). Local people such as hunters and foresters supported the expedition by giving information about (possible) wolf presence in the locality.

1.4. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular, including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report, can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

Project updates, reports and publications:

<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Diary for this expedition:

<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/germany-2023/>

Expedition details, background, pictures, videos, etc.:

<https://www.biosphere-expeditions.org/germany>

1.5. Acknowledgements

We would like to thank all the expedition citizen scientists, who not only dedicated their spare time to helping but also, through their expedition contributions, funded the research. Thank you also to those who brought their own cars and supported the expedition in this way too. Thank you to all our partners mentioned above, especially those at the 'Wolfsbüro' at NLWKN and to all those professionals who provided assistance and information. Special thanks also go to the local 'wolf commissioner' (Wolfsberater) Kenny Kenner and helpers working on a voluntary basis in support of the expedition. Their efforts and local knowledge were crucial to the success of our field work. Thanks also to the state forestry department (Niedersächsische Landesforsten) for their co-operation. Finally, thank you to the staff of BIO-Hotel Kenner's Landlust, led by Barbara & Kenny Kenner as well as to the staff at Naturcampus Bockum, led by Dr. Susanne Eich, for being such excellent hosts and making us feel at home, and to anonymous reviewers for helpful comments on the manuscript.

1.6. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist paid a contribution of €2,140 per person per seven-day period towards expedition costs. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special research equipment and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	51,072
 Expenditure	
Expedition base includes all food & services	10,986
Transport includes hire cars, fuel, taxis in Germany	3,980
Equipment and hardware includes research materials & gear etc. purchased internationally & locally	1,816
Staff includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff salaries and travel expenses	8,807
Administration includes miscellaneous fees & sundries	1,605
Team recruitment Germany as estimated % of annual PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	7,334
 Income – Expenditure	 16,544
 Total percentage spent directly on project	 68%

2. Monitoring wolves in Lower Saxony

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Wolf commissioner Lower Saxony

Charlotte Steinberg
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2.1. Introduction

The expedition's rationale, background, materials and methods, and training of citizen scientists are described in Schütte & Hammer (2018), Schütte & Hammer (2019), Schütte, Steinberg & Hammer (2020) and Schütte, Steinberg & Hammer (2023).

Wolf territories and population dynamics in Lower Saxony in 2022/2023

At the end of the monitoring year 2022/23 there were 184 confirmed wolf packs, 46 wolf pairs and 22 single resident wolves in Germany (DBBW 2024a) (Figs. 2.1a & 2.1b).

In the federal state of Lower Saxony, prior to the 2023 expedition commencing, the numbers of wolves were 46 wolf packs, three wolf pairs and two single wolves (April 2023). In December 2023, after the expedition, numbers increased to 50 wolf packs, four wolf pairs and two single wolves (Fig. 2.1c). At the time of writing (July 2024), Lower Saxony hosts 52 wolf packs, three wolf pairs and two single wolves (LJN 2023). This development (Table 2.1) illustrates that Lower Saxony offers suitable habitats, which are still not fully occupied by wolves.

Table 2.1. Wolf population dynamics in Lower Saxony April 2023 – May 2024.

Time	Wolf packs	Wolf pairs	Single wolves
April 2023	46	3	2
July 2023	42	4	2
October 2023	50	4	1
January 2024	50	4	2
July 2024	52	3	2

Study site and 2023 focus areas

Focus areas of the 2023 expedition are shown in Figures 2.1e (CORINE) and 2.1f (Google).

Focus areas were chosen in collaboration with local people (such as wolf commissioners, foresters, hunters) and authorities, such as the 'Wolfsbüro' at [NLWKN](#) (the wolf bureau at the state environment department). Such collaborations, especially with the wolf commissioners and the wolf bureau, are critical to the project's success. An additional and welcome side effect is that acceptance for the project, as well as citizen science projects in general and in the field of wildlife monitoring and research, are fostered.

Figure 2.1a.

Wolf territories in Germany on 30 April 2023 (DBBW 2024a).

Rudel (blue) = wolf pack

Paar (red) = wolf pair

Einzeltier (yellow) = single individual

The text reads “184 packs, 46 pairs, 22 territorial individuals are known, as well as 639 juveniles (17 packs crossing state boundaries). Territorial wolves are present in the states of Baden-Wurtemberg, Bavaria, Brandenburg, Hessen, Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, Lower Saxony, North Rhine-Westphalia, Rhineland-Palatinate, Saxony, Saxony-Anhalt, Schleswig-Holstein, Thuringia”.

Figure 2.1b. Distribution of wolves in Germany in 2022/2023 on the EEA grid system (BfN 2023).
Green cell = wolf presence confirmed in accordance with monitoring standards.
Green cell with black dot = wolf presence and reproduction confirmed

Figure 2.1c.

Wolf territories in Lower Saxony after the fourth quarter 2023 (LJN 2023a)

The reference reads:

Wolfsrudel (green) = wolf pack

Wolfsrudel (unbestätigt)* (pale green) = wolf pack (unconfirmed)*

Wolfspaar (orange) = wolf pair

Residenter Einzelwolf (blue) = resident individual

Unklar (gray) = unclear

Unter Beobachtung (white) = under observation

*) To be confirmed = pack existence through evidence of reproduction or more than two pack members has not yet been confirmed in the current monitoring season.

Figure 2.1d.

Distribution of wolves in Lower Saxony in the monitoring year 2022/2023 on the EEA grid system (LJN 2023b).

The reference reads:

1 piece of C1 hard evidence (light blue);
 2-5 pieces of C1 hard evidence (medium blue);
 More than 5 pieces of C1 hard evidence (dark blue).

Figure 2.1e. Land use cover in the study site and focus areas in 2023, map adapted from [CORINE](#).

Figure 2.1f. The 22 EEA grid cells covered during the 2023 surveys (indicated by yellow shading).

2.2. Methods & results

The data gathered by this study form part of the official wolf monitoring programme of Lower Saxony. All relevant data were integrated into the official database run by the Hunters association of Lower Saxony (LJN) (LJN 2023c). Those were reviewed by the official wolf monitoring programme and assessed by SCALP categories (see [Schütte & Hammer \(2018\)](#) and [Schütte & Hammer \(2019\)](#) for a description of these). Since our data form part of the official wolf monitoring programme, they were published in the official LJN quarterly and annual monitoring reports.

Over two weeks (i.e. two groups) of surveying, citizen scientists walked almost 800 km, covering 22 cells of the EEA 10 km x 10 km grid in total, some of them multiple times so that grid cells were covered a total of 35 times (Fig. 2.1f, Table 2.2a).

Table 2.2a. Number of grid cells and length of routes surveyed by the 2023 expedition teams during the two expedition weeks. Note that the team split into four or fewer groups each day.

Week	Grid cells (N)	Routes total (km)	Routes day 2** (km)	Routes day 3 (km)	Routes day 4 (km)	Routes day 5 (km)	Routes day 6 (km)
1	17	403.83	7.80	85.70	80.62	81.61	100.64
2	18	387.43	25.40	101.80	104.20	97.00	58.70
Total	35*	791.26					

*As all surveys took place within 22 grid cells, some grid cells were surveyed multiple times

** Day 2: training day, survey in one group

The expedition gathered 256 (putative) wolf scats, of which 216 were admitted for SCALP assessment. Forty-three of these 256 scats were too old or otherwise not suitable for analysis. Sixteen of the 216 samples were fresh enough (less than 48 hours old) to yield material for DNA analysis, which confirmed that the scats were indeed from wolf in all except one case. Of the 216 scats, 169 were suitable for dietary analysis (Table 2.2b)

Table 2.2b. Samples gathered by the expedition and submitted for analysis in 2023.

Scat samples total	Scat samples for dietary analysis	Scat samples for genetic analysis
216	169	16

Figure 2.2a. Proportions of expedition C1 scats (BE, in red) that have been included in the official monitoring programme (C1 scats sampled in the framework of the official monitoring programme of the “LJJN” – Landesjägerschaft – in Blue). No expedition due to COVID-19 in 2021, this year therefore excluded.

In total, 15 (7%) of the 216 samples collected were classified as C1 pieces of hard evidence, 28 (13%) as C2 confirmed observations and 164 (76%) as C3 unconfirmed observations (Fig. 2.2b), of which 109 (50% of the total) were scored as C3a (very likely to originate from wolf).

Figure 2.2b. The 216 scat samples collected by the expedition by their SCALP classification.

Fifteen of the 16 scat samples submitted to DNA analysis were shown to originate from wolf (one was too old for analysis). Wolf DNA was also detected on a feather found near to wolf pup paw prints, so that all in all, 17 genetic samples were analysed of which 16 were found to be from a wolf / wolves (all samples except one scat). Seven samples could be assigned to individual known wolves through comparison of existing DNA material. All in all, five male wolves and two female wolves were identified

A wolf sighting was recorded in the Königskrug territory and classed as C3 as there was no time to take a photograph or video.

Table 2.2c. Samples gathered by the expedition and submitted for analysis in 2023.

	Scat samples total	Scat samples for diet analysis	Scat samples for genetic analysis	Other genetic samples	Wolf sightings
Week 1	119	88	8	0	1
Week 2	97	81	8	1	1
Total	216	160	16	1	1

In week 1, eight scat samples were classed as C1, 19 as C2, 22 as C3 and 63 as C3a.

In week 2, seven scat samples were scored as C1, nine as C2, 33 as C3 and 46 as C3a (Fig. 2.2d).

Figure 2.2d. The 216 scat samples collected by the expedition in 2023 by their SCALP classification.

Food analysis

The scat samples collected by the expeditions in 2022 and 2023, which were suitable for dietary analysis, were handed over to the NLWKN after the expedition in 2023. There is currently a significant backlog of analysis due to staff shortages at the University of Veterinary Medicine in Hanover. This includes samples from expeditions in the years 2017 - 2022. As soon as results are known, they will be published in a report.

Genetics

Of the 17 genetic samples analysed, all except one could be assigned to the species “wolf”.

A total of six animals could be individually identified, four of which were previously unknown. Those four wolf individuals were identified based on samples that were collected within known territories. Therefore it is likely that they are offspring of the corresponding packs. For two of those, GW3635f and GW3636m, the exact pack of origin is unclear, but likely Garlstorf and Schneverdingen.

GW3614m was genetically assigned to the Ebstorf territory. The genetic evidence of this individual constitutes the proof of reproduction for the territory for the year 2023.

GW2951m, which was detected based on samples collected in the Amt Neuhaus territory, was identified as the new resident male wolf there (Tables 2.2.d & e).

Table 2.2.d. Overall results of genetic analyses.

DNA wolf	DNA no wolf	Species undetermined	Total DNA samples
16	0	1	17

Table 2.2.e. Detailed results of genetic analyses.

No.	ID	Sex	Territory (sampled)	Comment
1	GW1027m	Male	Ebstorf	Pack male
2	GW3635f	Female	Garlstorf	
3	GW872f	Female	Amt Neuhaus	Pack female
4	GW2951m	Male	Amt Neuhaus	Pack male
5	GW3614m	Male	Ebstorf	Proof of reproduction
6	GW3636m	Male	Schneverdingen	

2.3. Discussion & conclusions

Efficiency of effort – data quantity and quality

The citizen science expedition of 2023 has once again made a very significant contribution to wolf monitoring efforts in Lower Saxony in terms of quantity:

With 216 (potential) wolf scats, 14% of the official wolf monitoring programme's scats between January and December 2023 were collected by the Biosphere Expeditions citizen science expedition. This is even more remarkable since those 14% were collected during only two weeks of intensive sampling effort.

In terms of quality, the work of the citizen scientists was excellent too:

The amount of C1 scats collected by the expedition (n = 15) was more than the amount of C1 scats sampled by the rest of the official monitoring programme (n = 9). The evaluation of scats sampled over the years (2017-2023, 2021 excluded) shows that the proportion of C1 scats sampled in the framework of the expeditions make up 42% of all C1 scats of the official monitoring programme.

Overall, these results demonstrate clearly that with only a day and a half of training, citizen scientists can make high quality and quantity contributions to the official wolf monitoring programme.

Areas of wolf activity

Most of the scat samples classed as C1 and C2 (n=43) were found within the wolf territories of Ebstorf (n=8), Bad Bodenteich (n=7), Amt Neuhaus (n=7) and Schneverdingen (n=6).

The key factor for successful surveys is not only the contribution of citizen scientists, but also availability of information about wolf activity and territories in the areas surveyed. A targeted and therefore highly successful search for wolf signs, such as demonstrated by this expedition, is only possible through good information flow between the expedition and local stakeholders with detailed knowledge of wildlife and wilderness, such as the local wolf commissioners, foresters and hunters.

Wolf population dynamics

A total of six wolf individuals were identified via DNA samples collected by the expedition in 2023. Table 2.3a compares this to results in other years.

Table 2.3a. Number of wolves identified by DNA samples of the expedition years.

2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
6	10	10	4	0*	8	6

* No expedition due to COVID-19 pandemic

Exact information about territory borders, kinship and offspring or migration routes can only be gleaned partially by the official wolf monitoring programme. For a comprehensive picture, there is simply not enough information in the form of DNA samples. In other words, despite considerable efforts, not least of the expedition, many more samples and a well-planned active monitoring effort are necessary.

For the monitoring year 2022/23 reproduction was detected in 92% of all wolf packs in Germany (DBBW 2023). This means that an increase in the wolf population is highly likely and that more territories will be occupied throughout the country, Lower Saxony included as there are still unoccupied and suitable areas.

In areas with high wolf density, one can observe that the number of territories increases more slowly or not at all while the number of wolves in single territories partly gets larger due to a phenomenon called “double reproduction”: Within a pack, not only one female but two female wolves (often mother and daughter wolf) produce offspring from one male wolf. Since this phenomenon occurs with the increase of the wolf population in Germany, it is assumed that wolves take advantage of a higher number of wolf individuals in the packs: The more wolves that live in a pack, the better the territory can be defended against wolves of other packs.

Therefore, active monitoring not only remains essential to track changes and shifts of territories as well as changes in pack composition, but also gets more and more difficult and at the same time increasingly important. This also means that Citizen Science projects such as the Biosphere Expeditions will play an increasingly important role beyond the background monitoring of the increasing wolf population, in order to gain information about numbers and especially borders of territories as well as individuals.

During over 791 km of survey effort, one fleeting wolf encounter was registered by the expedition in 2023 (2022: one encounter over 837 km, 2020: zero encounters over 246 km, 2019: two encounters over 743 km, 2018: one encounter over 750 km, 2017: zero encounters over 1,100 km). From this it is clear that the chances of encountering a wolf during daytime, even when looking for wolf signs in suitable habitat, are very small due to the elusive character of the species. Reports in the media and by anti-wolf campaigners of the state portraying wolves as not very shy and “conspicuous” are clearly exaggerated.

Wolf feeding ecology

Results of the analysis of wolf scats are based on indigestible prey remains. They do not represent the food spectrum of wolves in general, but give indications about the food items of wolves, as well as information about more and less important prey species. Based on scat analysis, statements about the acquisition process of food items are not possible – they may have been either actively hunted or ingested as carrion.

The investigation of the 45 scats sampled during the expedition in 2017 indicated that wild ungulates (mainly roe deer, wild boar and red deer) represent the food base of wolves in Lower Saxony. It was significant that no remains of livestock were found. This corroborates previous studies, which showed that the proportion of livestock in the wolf’s diet is very low or absent altogether (DBBW 2018). This may vary regionally, depending on the availability of wildlife prey and insufficiently protected livestock - wolves attack, kill and consume

livestock. Even if livestock might be underrepresented in scat samples to a certain degree as livestock owners are legally obliged to remove carcasses from their meadows, the data collected by the expedition in 2017 strongly suggests that, in general, its consumption is rare compared to the consumption of wild ungulates. The analysis of scats collected in the following years is expected to shed more light on this, in particular whether this pattern is maintained.

From scats that were sampled all over Germany and analysed for food items, it is known that the food spectrum of wolves is subject to seasonal fluctuations which are related to the availability of (young) wild ungulates: whereas wild boar mainly occurs in scats sampled in spring when piglets are available, scats sampled in summer mainly contain remains of red deer, as calves are born in the summer months. In contrast, roe deer as a medium-size prey is consumed at a similar proportion throughout the year.

Also, weather conditions have an influence: in years in which many nuts and fruits are available in autumn and with mild winters, the proportion of wild boar in the diet is higher compared to years with cold winters and less food for wild boar. Also, there are indications that certain habits are determined by individual preferences of the pack members (e.g. frequency of certain secondary prey species such as small mammals and hares in the food spectrum) (Holzapfel et. al 2019).

Local stakeholder and cooperations

Our main aim was to collect indirect wolf signs, with an emphasis on finding scat samples in order to assist official wolf monitoring efforts and supplement the wolf monitoring database. This aim was achieved. In addition, data collected by the expedition also allowed important conclusions to be drawn about some of the wolf territories and newly identified individual wolves. We conducted the 2023 surveys by and large in areas with similar or the same survey routes as in the previous years (Schütte and Hammer 2019 & 2020, Schütte, Steinberg and Hammer 2023) but new areas were added too. Thanks to the notable and much welcomed cooperation of local stakeholders such as wolf commissioners and foresters first and foremost, but also hunters, study areas could be selected with a high degree of specificity, so that a high number of usable scat samples could be collected. This is also the main reason why the inaugural 2017 expedition collected only 76 scats with four groups (Schütte and Hammer 2018), whereas the 2018 expedition collected 218 scats with two groups and the 2019 expedition 156 scats, also with two groups.

In addition, and thanks to the cooperation of the State Forestry Department (Niedersächsische Landesforsten), new areas were included in our monitoring activities and we were explicitly asked by the State Forestry Department to conduct surveys in some areas. This is in marked contrast to the State Forestry Department's conduct during the expedition's inaugural year of 2017, when the State Forestry Department forbade the expedition to enter certain areas due to smear and misinformation campaigns by anti-wolf elements amongst the hunting community and/or political class (see Schütte and Hammer 2018 for details). The expedition appreciates the trust and cooperation now shown by the State Forestry Department.

It is also worth noting that hostility towards the expedition shown in 2017 (Schütte and Hammer 2018) and to a lesser extent in 2018 (Schütte and Hammer 2019) by the media and the anti-wolf lobby has ebbed away. It is unknown whether this is because it has been accepted that the expedition's efforts are worthwhile or whether other targets have been found.

Summary

The wolf has returned to Germany to stay. Those who do not like this and employ misinformation, populism and demagoguery to incite conflict and highly emotional, politically charged and irrational arguments against wolves must be countered each time with calm, factual and science-based discourse. Those who are exposed to real risks through wolves, namely livestock owners, should be listened to, supported and compensated as necessary, ideally through an effective, unbureaucratic and nationwide support and advice system.

We believe that a system of regionally active, trained professionals is needed, who can respond to questions about and issues around wolves directly, unbureaucratically and competently, and act close to the ground and in close cooperation with the local population and stakeholders. So far the federal and state governments, as well as agricultural and veterinarian bodies, have failed to create appropriate structures, which are necessary when a large carnivore returns to a cultural landscape.

In addition, we believe that more must be done to stop and prevent illegal wolf killings. The records of wolves found dead, taken since 2003, show that illegal killing of this protected species (a criminal offence in Germany) is the second most common form of death (9%) after traffic accidents (76%); the remaining 15% are due to diseases or other reasons (DBBW 2024b). A particularly sad example of an illegal killing is the male wolf GW1039m, whose existence was shown by the expedition in 2018, only to be found shot dead shortly after the expedition in August 2018.

Just prior to the expedition in 2023, the severed head of a wolf was found in front of the centre for environmental education by the nature conservation NGO Naturschutzbund Deutschland (NABU) in Leiferde. Unknown people had deposited it there at the beginning of April. One month later it was clear that the head belonged to a female wolf named GW3200f which originated from the territory of Ringelah. Just weeks before, the dead body of a wolf without a head had been found in the same area. A subsequent investigation showed that the body belonged to the female wolf GW1861f of the Ringelah pack. However, it could not be confirmed that the head belonged to the same individual. Presumably there is a high percentage of unreported killings. Here, the investigative authorities and courts must work harder to stop this and prosecute perpetrators, as [for example in the neighbouring federal state of Saxony-Anhalt](#).

While there are challenges associated with wolf presence, there are opportunities too. The wolf-baiting and anti-wolf headlines seem to have been largely ignored so far. We see the biggest potential in rural communities generating income through tourism by combining the experience of nature and the presence of wolves. There are examples of companies and entrepreneurs in Lower Saxony who have recognised the value of the wolf for tourism. Furthermore, wolf presence can contribute to the regulation of browsing by large wild herbivores and thus be supportive to regeneration of forests (CHWOLF 2020).

Next to large-scale, national issues, this project on a Lower Saxony state and regional scale, and in close collaboration with the State Wolf Bureau, not only reached its goals, it exceeded, now also in its seventh year, all expectations. It is clear that the efforts of well-trained citizen scientists deployed as part of a well-planned fieldwork expedition can be very productive and that highly valuable data can be acquired through targeted active wolf monitoring work conducted by citizen scientists. This refutes those who doubted that citizen science could make a useful contribution. These doubts were especially prevalent amongst hunters, hunting associations, some forestry officials and landowners before and during the inaugural 2017 expedition, but has changed in some quarters after the results of the 2017 expedition were published.

The State Forestry Department now supports the expedition and it is hoped that the results presented here will encourage others to do so as well. The authors are, and always have been, ready to collaborate in the spirit of successful wolf conservation and human-wolf co-existence in Lower Saxony.

Recommendations for future expeditions

The citizen science expeditions should be repeated on an annual basis and they should:

- Adapt/improve methods and logistics as necessary, based on an annual review of activities.
- Gain support from more wolf commissioners and district nature conservation authorities for active monitoring in areas of specific interest.

Improve communications with stakeholders:

- Repeat offers to stakeholders, such as hunting associations, forestry departments and landowners, to use/involve/allow the efforts of Biosphere Expeditions, e.g. camera trapping and sign surveys.

Involve local, national and international citizen scientists:

- Seek grant and other support, or fund internally, free placements for local people on the expedition.
- Work with the media to encourage more local participation.

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Appendix I: Week-by-week survey results

Effort & results week 1

Survey days	5	
EEA 10x10 km grid cells covered	17	
Scats collected	122	
Day	Distance covered by teams (km)	Remarks
Sun, 07 July	16.8	One training group only
Mon, 08 July	116.4	Maximum four small groups
Tue, 09 July	76.53	Maximum four small groups
Wed, 10 July	91.50	Maximum four small groups
Thu, 11 July	102.60	Maximum four small groups
Total	403.83	

Figure Ia. 17 EEA grid cells covered during week 1 of the 2023 expedition (indicated as yellow shading).

Effort & results week 2

Survey days	5	
EEA 10x10 km grid cells covered	18	
Scats collected	94	
Day	Distance covered by teams (km)	Remarks
Sat, 13 / Sun, 14 July	37.2	One training group only
Mon, 15 July	77.22	Maximum four small groups
Tue, 16 July	106.88	Maximum four small groups
Wed, 17 July	72.68	Maximum four small groups
Thu, 18 July	93.45	Maximum four small groups
Total	387.43	

Figure 1b. 18 EEA grid cells covered during week 2 of the 2023 expedition (indicated as yellow shading).